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ENGINEERING GRAPHICS CONCEPT INVENTORY (EGCI) CRITERION VALIDITY ANALYSIS

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INTRODUCTION

At the onset of a new course, students have prior knowledge on which they develop their understanding of a particular subject. Some of this knowledge is due to the interpretation of a collection of experiences and teachings that the students have amassed along their educational journey, some of which have been misunderstood. Such misconceptions can be a barrier for deeper understanding if not identified and addressed. There is a need for more accurate tools to better determine the misconceptions that exist in order to prevent

further perpetuation of those misconceptions in students. One instrument that can identify such issues is a concept inventory.

A concept inventory is a tool to aid in the identification of deep seated misconceptions held by students and to measure student learning. The antecedent Force Concept Inventory [1] has led to the development of a number of concept inventories, for example, in thermodynamics [2], heat transfer [3], statics [4] and now engineering graphics [5]. The use of concept inventories across different branches of engineering could prove to be useful in assessing effectiveness of instruction and providing insight on teaching methods that promote improved student understanding.

1. ENGINEERING GRAPHICS CONCEPT INVENTORY

1.1 Background

Engineering graphics is a branch of engineering which is common in a wide range of engineering curricula in the United States and was determined to be a suitable candidate for the development of a concept inventory. In 2013, a research team assembled to create an instrument that would serve as a nationally standardized means of assessing misconceptions in engineering graphics. The collaboration of faculty, staff and doctoral students at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University (ERAU), Purdue University, Penn State Behrend, NC State University and The Ohio State University has led to the development of the Engineering Graphics Concept Inventory.

The development of the instrument began with the consultation of graphics experts who formed a Delphi panel. One-hundred-and-twenty unique engineering graphics topics were originally identified by the panel. These topics were later coalesced into 10 fundamental concepts and then further distilled into the five concepts that are currently identified and tested by the instrument [6]. A face validity study was conducted whereby the graphics experts reviewed the items in the instrument to verify that they were testing what they were designed to test. The experts confirmed that all items assessed the intended concepts, which suggests good face validity.

1.2 Item Selection

The current instrument is a 30-item multiple choice instrument that tests five engineering graphics concepts: sections, projection theory, mapping between 2D and 3D, planar geometry and dimensioning. The items were carefully selected through an iterative process to have a range of difficulty and be of sufficient discrimination (above 0.30). The distractors in each item were judiciously chosen to reflect a single misconception, such that they would be associated with a particular misunderstanding. The data used in this paper was taken from the fourth iteration – the “delta” version – and presently the instrument is undergoing its fifth iteration – the “epsilon” version. Figure 1 shows a sample item from the EGCI which tests the projection theory, specifically orthographic projection of inclined surfaces.

Select the set of views that show surface “A” correctly labeled in the top view and the right hand side view.

Figure 1: Sample Question from the EGCI on Projection Theory

Inclined surfaces appear as an angled edge in one orthographic view and as a surface in the other two orthographic views. From the right side view of every option it is seen that there are two angled lines which correspond to two inclined surfaces, both of which span the entire height of the object. Option C is the correct choice – surface A appears as a surface view in both the front view and the top view, and as an inclined edge in the right side view. Distractor A has surface A labeled as a surface three times, suggesting that A is an oblique surface, and not an inclined surface. Distractor B has surface A labelled as a surface only once, and as an edge twice, which is the behavior of a normal surface. However, when Surface A is projected onto the right side view it aligns with the inclined edge. Distractor D has surface A labelled as a surface twice and as an edge only once which is consistent with the behavior of inclined surfaces in orthographic views, however, the edge labeled in the top view is horizontal which would imply that surface A is a normal surface. The isometric view of the object, which is not included in the instrument, is shown in Figure 2 with surface A correctly labelled.

Fig. 2. Isometric View of the Object from the Sample Question on Projection Theory

1.3 Instrument Validity

Validity is the measure of the meaningfulness of a test. In order to determine whether the EGCI is indeed measuring what it is designed to measure the validity must be considered. Criterion validity is a measure of the relationship between two different sets of scores and is typically analyzed in terms of concurrent validity or predictive validity. Concurrent validation is the assessment of whether an instrument is able to distinguish between groups that in theory it should be able to differentiate between by comparing the scores to a known standard; predictive validation is the measure of the ability of an instrument to predict competence. For concurrent validation the EGCI scores were compared to the grade points of students who were enrolled in EGR 120 – a course in graphical communication. Predictive validation has not yet been measured and will require analysis of data collected over a longer period of time.

2. METHOD

2.1 EGCI Platform and Participants

The instrument was administered through the survey software Qualtrics to first-year engineering students at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University, Penn State Behrend and Purdue. Two-hundred-and-twenty-nine ERAU students participated in the delta version of the instrument at the end of the Fall 2017 semester, 29 of which opted out of having their scores included in the analysis. Five different faculty members from the department of Engineering Fundamentals at ERAU, with a range of teaching experience from one year to 10 years, administered the instrument to students enrolled in their respective EGR 120 sections. ERAU was chosen for this analysis because of the ease of access to the relevant information while data from the other institutions was still being correlated.

The instrument gathered demographic data to record participant information. The participants then responded to the 30 multiple-choice items. The instrument required the participants to make a selection before moving on to the next item, which could be changed before final submission of the instrument. For data to be considered in the analysis, participants had to have responded to all of the items. While the overall scores attained by the students were further parsed into the performance for each concept, the particular responses to each item were not linked to the individuals.

2.2 Data Collected

The course grades for the EGR 120 students who participated in the EGCI were collected for the Fall 2017 semester. Grade points were assigned to correspond to letter grades. Table 1 shows the allocation of grade points per letter grade.

Table 1. Grade Points per Letter Grade

Letter Grade	Percentage (%)	Grade Points
A	90.00≥	4
B	80.00-89.99	3
C	70.00-79.99	2
D	60.00-69.99	1
F	<60.00	0

The participants were grouped based on their overall course grades and the mean EGCI scores for each group were calculated and analyzed. The null hypothesis states that there is no correlation between the performance in the EGCI and the overall course performance.

3. RESULTS

The overall scores of the students who participated in the EGCI are shown in Table 2 versus grade point. IBM SPSS was used to conduct the analysis of the results. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was calculated for the individual EGCI scores earned and the course grade received. The coefficient was found to be 0.305 at a significance level of 0.01.

Table 2. EGCI Mean Scores per Grade Point

Grade Points	4	3	2	1	0
Number of Students	60	79	47	10	4
EGCI Mean Score	20.02	16.44	14.96	16.30	14.00
Standard Deviation	5.83	4.78	5.56	6.20	4.24
Standard Error	0.41	0.34	0.39	0.44	0.30

A total of 200 students' scores were considered in the analysis. The mean scores per grade point are shown graphically in Figure 3, along with the standard error per grade point. It is evident that there is a general trend for the EGCI mean score to increase with the grade point which suggests that the students who score better in the class generally perform better in the instrument. There is a discrete data point which does not follow the general trend for performance – students who earn 1 grade point, i.e. those who score a D in the course, have a higher mean score than students who earn 2 grade points, i.e. those who score a C in the course. The source of this outlier is believed to be due to a low n , as the sample size for students who score a D in the course is relatively small when compared those who score a C, and therefore a single student in this group who scores well has the ability to greatly impact the mean of the group as is seen in this case. Additionally, multiple choice assessments do not have the ability to determine when a student might have correctly guessed an answer and the performance of those who scored a D in the course could be attributed to guessing. Finally, there are only four students who earned an F in EGR 120, so even though the mean EGCI score for those students follows the trend, it is of negligible concern for this study.

Fig. 3. EGCI Mean Score vs. Grade Point

The sample size for low performing students is low and the concurrent validity is not an adequate representation of the effectiveness of the instrument for the low performers. However, as data is collected for subsequent semesters it will be possible to predict a trend and further prove the criterion validity due to an increased sample size. This will form the basis of a predictive validity study.

Figure 4 shows the trend for students who pass the course with a C grade or better. The sample sizes are adequate to provide significance to the trend. The R^2 value provides an indication of how well the data conforms to the trend. The R^2 value for students who pass the course is 0.9463 compared to 0.7088 for the original pool of participants which implies that there is less scatter about the line of best fit.

Fig. 4. EGCI Mean Score vs. Grade Point for Passing Students

4. CONCLUSION

To gain the most utility out of an instrument, it is critical to ensure that it is measuring what it is designed to measure. Validity considerations lend credibility to the assessment and prove its effectiveness. Studying the concurrent validity provides indication of criterion validity by comparing the results to a standard which is already recognized. An adequate sample size is necessary in order to obtain significant results. The data collected revealed a trend in performance and a positive correlation between the mean score in the EGCI and the number of grade points received for a course. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected – students who perform well in the EGCI generally perform well in the graphics course, which implies good criterion validity.

A study of predictive validation will likely further support the criterion validity of the instrument, and will allow the authors to further consider the performance of the lower scoring students given the larger sample size. However, at this stage of the study the low n of the lower scoring students make those scores fairly insignificant.

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